

of $[\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3]^{3+}$ (pn = propylenediamine) is somewhat disturbing. The association constants were also utilised to determine the radii of the ion-pairs from Bjerrum equation. Unfortunately the Bjerrum distances (Table 3) did not agree well with those obtained from the sum of the anion radii and the cation radii, both being obtained from Stoke's law. However, such discrepancies have also been noted by Jenkins and Monk⁵.

TABLE 3—APPROXIMATE RADII OF $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$ AND ION-PAIRS

Cation/anion	Radius from Stoke's law a(A)	Ion pair	Radius from Stoke's law a(A)	Radius from Bjerrum equation a(A)
$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$	4.03			
Cl^-	1.20	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Cl}\}^{2+}$	5.23	4.28
Br^-	1.18	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Br}\}^{2+}$	5.21	6.11
I^-	1.19	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{I}\}^{2+}$	5.22	7.38
SO_4^{--}	2.29	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{SO}_4\}^+$	6.32	5.03

We have been investigating a number of other inert cobalt (III) complexes namely $[\text{Co}(\text{PhBigH})_3]^{3+}$ (PhBigH = phenylbiguanide), $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ (AA = dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline). Details of these studies will be published in due course.

References

1. A. K. DE, N. N. GHOSH and P. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **27**, 493.
2. P. RAY and N. K. DUTT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 81.
3. D. BANERJEA and B. CHAKRAVARTY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1233.
4. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, *Electrolyte Solutions*, 2nd Ed. Butterworths, London, 1968.
5. I. L. JENKINS and C. B. MONK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 68.

Dipterocarpol from Wood Extractives of Dipterocarpaceae

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SEVERAL *Dipterocarpaceae* species grow in Bangladesh. Dipterocarpol has been isolated directly from the petroleum extract of the weed of *D. turbinatus*, a species available here in abundance. It has been identified as hydroxydammarone-II on the basis of elemental analysis, m.p., infrared absorption and of its conversion to dammarenediol-II. Earlier it was isolated from the balsams¹⁻³ and the hydrolytic

products of the weed extractives⁴ of some *Dipterocarpaceae* species and shown identical with hydroxydammarone-II, a tetracyclic triterpene derivative, isolated from dammar,^{5,6} a group of natural resins originating from the trees of *Dipterocarpaceae* family.

Experimental

Dried powdered weed of *D. turbinatus* was extracted with petroleum ether (40°–60°) at room temperature for 48 hrs; the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure, when a yellowish gummy mass (0.61%) deposited. On standing for a couple of days a crystalline solid appeared in the gum. On careful washing with light petroleum ether, gummy portion dissolved preferentially leaving behind a white material which afforded from light petroleum ether crystals, m.p. 126°–128°, resolidified, and then m.p., 132°–134°. The crystals (500 mg.) were chromatographed on alumina in petroleum ether (40°–60°) and eluted first with light petroleum ether, then with benzene and finally with methanol. Eluates from petroleum ether gave a trace of gum, and from methanol yielded crystalline product (415 mg.) which, on further crystallisations from methanol appeared as plates, m.p. 127°–128° (resolidified and then m.p. 135°–136°); $[\alpha]_D^{22} = +67.08$ (c. 1.05 in CHCl_3); infrared bands at 3570, 1695, 1440 and 1375 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 81.3; H, 11.2%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.4; H, 11.4%). [For dipterocarpol Cosserat³ records m.p. 127° (resolidifies and then m.p. 132°–134°); $[\alpha]_D = +65^\circ$; Mclean⁴ gives m.p. 132°–134°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +67^\circ$ (c. 1.09 in CHCl_3). It gave the same colour reactions as Hydroxydammarone-II as recorded by Mills⁵. Its semicarbazone melted at 204°–206° (Crabbe⁷ gives m.p. 206°–207; Mclean⁴ records m.p. 203°–205°).

Reduction of dipterocarpol: Dipterocarpol (200 mg) was reduced in methanol (75 ml) with sodium (4 g.), the product isolated and chromatographed over alumina in benzene. Benzene-ether (19:1) elute gave a product which on crystallisation twice from methanol appeared as crystals of dammarenediol (75 mg), m.p. 130°–132° (recorded⁵ m.p. 130°–132°).

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References

1. L. VAN ITALLIE, *Arch. Pharm.* 1912, **250**, 204.
2. D. H. GOODSON, F. E. KING and T. J. KING, *Chem. & Ind.* 1956, 190.
3. L. COSSEBAT, G. OURISSON and T. TAKAHASHI, *Chem & Ind.* 1956, 190.
4. J. MCLEAN and W. E. WATTS, *J. Org. Chem.* 1960, **25**, 1263.
5. J. S. MILLS and A. E. A. WERNER, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1955, 3132.
6. J. S. MILLS, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1956, 2196.
7. P. Crabbe, G. OURISSON and TAKAHASHI, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, **3**, 279.